

Concept for the testing of automated functions in medical devices

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Abstract: This paper presents a concept for testing automated functions of medical devices. Therefore, an ontology-based testing approach is selected to be utilized for medical applications. The tests are used for examination at the system level. In doing so, the concept for the test system consists of two main components. On the one hand, a software to define relevant test scenarios and, on the other hand, a test bench to apply the relevant test scenarios. Finally, the key steps of the concept are discussed. This will be done exemplarily for autonomous functions in mechanical ventilation.

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I. Introduction

The shortage of qualified personnel in intensive care units is a well-known problem [1], which has become more apparent in the context of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. For this reason, advanced clinical decision support systems capable of performing functions independently may be beneficial. These systems have the potential to relieve burden of medical staff and to allow greater focus on individual therapy decisions and patient care. In some areas of medical technology, semi-autonomous functions already exist, such as insulin application in the therapy of diabetes mellitus. Here, the blood glucose level is measured regularly, and an appropriate amount of insulin is automatically administered. Lal et al. [2] found in a study that one reason for discontinuation of automated therapy was inadequate response to patient behavior. For example, the device could not adequately respond to unusual stresses such as sports. As exemplified, it is necessary to test and analyze automated systems thoroughly for exceptional cases in order to determine and ensure safety. For this reason, an ontology-based procedure is being developed which should be able to identify and test critical and rare scenarios. The considered automation level of the medical system corresponds to automation level 4, a system in which the clinician is not part of the control loop and can leave the room, as described by Rostalski et. al [7]. The main requirement for the medical system is therefore the ability to independently reach and maintain a safe state that ensures the patients' safety and does not contradict the therapy goals. Finally, the developed concept should be able to proof these properties.

II. Test coverage of autonomous systems

Autonomous systems need to be able to properly sense their contextual environment in order to provide the correct input in accordance with the therapy goal. For practical application on humans, it must be ensured that these systems operate reliably and can handle all foreseeable and

most of unforeseeable situations. This includes, most importantly, ensuring that the system can respond adequately even to rare exceptional cases. Therefore, all theoretically possible situations have to be tested, which is expensive and, in most cases, practically impossible. To address this issue in the automotive industry a test-system was developed [4]. In doing so, to ensure safety is the key goal. With highly automated functions, such as the highway pilot, wrong decisions of the system can lead to fatal consequences [4]. It was determined by Maurer et al. [3] that it would be necessary to test a highway pilot 6.62 billion test kilometers to prove its' safety. A possible approach to achieve sufficient test coverage without testing all possible variants, is to make an adequate preselection of representative test cases. For this reason, an ontology-based testing approach was developed for the automotive sector [4]. The ontology-based testing approach can be used to create simulations that identify critical scenarios. These critical scenarios can then be physically evaluated on a test bench and in turn significantly reduce the number of required physical tests [4].

III. Proposed test concept

Figure 1 shows the proposed approach for medical devices based on the test method from the automotive sector [4]. In an ontology-based test approach, a database forms the basis for the selection of test cases. This database is initially setup and is maintained on a regular base to provide the needed information (e. g. case studies, regulations or standards). A source of data for the generation of test cases might be failure reports from the installed base. The data is converted into a processable language using Model-Based-System-Engineering (MBSE) [5, 6], so that it can be read both by humans and machines. This includes sequence diagrams, activity diagrams and others [5, 6]. From the logical scenarios represented in the ontology, an automated and systematic test simulation will be generated. The generated

Figure 1: The figure shows the test concept for automated functions in medical devices.

test simulation shall consist of several scenario levels (see figure 2). These levels contain static as well as dynamic aspects adapted from the automotive concept proposed by J. Mazzega et al. [4]. Static levels of interest would be, e. g. body weight/fat and muscle distribution, or age. A dynamic level would be, for example, the progression of the disease. The test scenarios can be described from a combination of these individual levels. Optimization algorithms can then be used to identify critical scenarios that may result in harm to a patient. These algorithms would optimize a main criterion, like potential harm the patient. The results are used to decide, which scenarios are to be considered critical. For the optimization, a local search or gradient based methods can be used [4].

Figure 2: The figure shows exemplary parameters for the scenario generation. The patient characteristics are to be combined considering dependencies between the individual levels.

The identified critical scenarios can then be executed on a test bench for further investigation. The evaluation on a test bench requires a device that can emulate the patient, as well as external disturbance at the devices' interface to the patient. A key requirement for such a simulator is high flexibility to represent many patients with a variety of (patho-) physiologic conditions. This may require a more technical design of the patient emulator, then provided by the existing simulators, which are commonly designed in analogy to the physiological principle, e. g. as using bellows as lung surrogate. To exemplary implement the proposed approach, a lung simulator that can replicate a larger variation of physical conditions at the upper respiratory tract is being developed within this project.

The tests carried out on the test bench are to be evaluated automatically on the basis of the criteria defined in the input data (see figure 1). These criteria refine the main aspect for identifying the critical scenarios. This includes, for example, that depending on the simulated patient, specific

pressure ratios in the lungs must not be exceeded during the ventilation test and that patients are adequately ventilated. The output of this test process serves as evidence for the safety of the automated medical functions. For this safety evidence, based on J. Mazzega et al. [4], the absence of safety violations can be considered for the most likely critical cases and for systematically determined critical cases.

IV. Conclusions

The ontology-based test concept for automated systems in medical devices presented here is intended to provide both high test coverage and evidence of safety. Using a practical example with an automated ventilation function, it will be investigated whether the approach from the automotive industry can be transferred to medical technology. For the next steps, the parts of the test system have to be implemented and selected test cases have to be defined.

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